

Learning from NBS and NEB projects

Synthesis of key findings from successful NBS and
NEB projects

Deliverable D1.1

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1. Introduction

1.1 INNATURE project summary

This document is Deliverable D1.1 and presents key lessons learned from other NBS and NEB projects and research that form the theoretical and evidence-based foundation for the Horizon Europe project **INNATURE: Enhancing Biodiversity and Social Inclusion by Transforming Europe’s Living Environments**.

The INNATURE project aims to re-imagine and accelerate new living futures and ‘next practices’ across Europe by co-creating five diverse Nature Based Solutions (NBS) demonstration cases across Europe (Belgium, Denmark, Finland, Romania, UK) that are **inclusive (co-created together), beautiful and sustainable, the three key pillars of the New European Bauhaus (NEB)**.

It will do so by **bringing biodiversity and people diversity together at all levels** (i.e. diverse communities, artists and designers, ecologists, researchers, policymakers, and other stakeholders) and to monitor the performance and /un)intended consequences of the NBS that are NEB-by-design over time from different perspectives (e.g., biodiversity, ecological, social, technical and economic).

Figure 1. The INNATURE project concentrates on enhancing biodiversity and social inclusion by transforming Europe’s Living environments. Image depicts Karen’s Minde Axis flood prevention project, a biodiverse rainwater catchment area in Copenhagen, Denmark. Photo: Sofie Pelsmakers

1.2 Purpose of this document

One of the first tasks we collectively and transnationally undertook was setting the foundation of the INNATURE project by the mapping of Nature Based Solutions (NBS) locally and globally (Task T1.1), with a particular focus on NBS that reflect the New European Bauhaus values (NEB) of **inclusivity (working together), sustainability, and beauty** (i.e., being locally meaningful). The aim was to set a strong evidence-based foundation of the current state of the art to enable us to reflect and learn from this to further advance the co-creation of the INNATURE NBS that are NEB-by-Design. This document sets out a summary of the key findings from reviewing existing projects, case studies and research.

We specifically looked at key issues with regards to implementation of the **solutions** (i.e., technical, non-technical, social, environmental, etc.); **common goals and methods of creation and communication**, alongside understanding and mapping any **unintended consequences** (either positive or negative). This knowledge (where available) and **key barriers** but also **opportunities** and **lessons learned** were synthesised and reflected on for potential transferability to INNATURE demonstration case locations and wider EU scaling-up. These key reflections can be found in summary Tables throughout this document and are further synthesised in a four-paged [Executive Summary](#) (tinted pages). For how this mapping was undertaken, see Section 3: [Data collection and analyses methods](#).

As an initial research foundation summary, it is also made publicly available as a catalyst for others to reflect on and further build on. As an initial foundational summary, it is envisaged that this knowledge basis will be added to and expanded over the INNATURE project duration, making this document (D1.1) a dynamic deliverable with future revisions.

In total, one hundred carefully selected listings were created and can be found in a full resource database list in the [APPENDIX](#) but also as an Open Access Excel database on the [INNATURE Collective Zenodo community](#) website. Of these listings most were research projects or case studies, as we specifically focused on the mapping of successful NBS and NEB projects. Research articles are also listed, either as a primary source or in connection to the project or cases found.

We also highlighted several projects as part of European initiatives and funding mechanisms that seemed particularly fruitful for future collaboration and clustering activities. However, general principles of approaches to potential clustering activities are unfolded in Deliverable D7.1 - the INNATURE Communication, Dissemination and Clustering Plan.

2. Executive Summary

This four-paged Executive Summary is intended as an overall, more generalised summary overview of the key findings of the reviewed NBS and NEB projects, which are then unfolded in more detail in later sections and exemplified with specific projects and cases from the extensively reviewed project and literature database. For ease of navigation, links are provided to the more detailed sections in the document. The executive summary highlights key findings regarding the state of the art and research gaps, followed by specific lessons for the INNATURE project along three main themes: **1.) NBS that are NEB; 2.) Transferability and 3.) Scalability**, which is how the remainder of the document is structured (after presenting our research mapping methods in Section 3: [Data collection and analyses methods](#)).

2.1 Summary State of the Art and research gaps

Summarising the learnings from successful NBS and NEB projects brought up emerging and ongoing paradigm shifts and gaps in research knowledge on NBS, as set out in Table 1.

Table 1. Summary State of the Art and research gaps

- The importance of **NBS multifunctionality** is becoming better understood and this can be improved by design, especially if systems thinking is applied, with attention to regenerative processes. At the same time this understanding highlights the requirement for long term monitoring of the social and ecological processes and their outcomes.
- An increased awareness was noted that **acting with nature requires to act with self-organising processes** and this **methodological development** requires and provides learnings for citizen participation and vice versa.
- Another paradigm shift requires that we **unlearn human centism to gain multi-species perspectives** in cities, including also natural entities such as rivers. Implementing this novel understanding into the design and maintenance of urban environments **requires the development of new interdisciplinary approaches and practical tools**.
- Relational practices that take the whole of human relations into account are re-emerging; this is made visible e.g. in contextual learning while building low-tech solutions together. This requires stronger **acknowledgement of issues related to equity** in diverse societal and environmental conditions at the global scale; cases are Europe focused, creating potential global knowledge gaps.

2.2 Lessons for the INNATURE project

2.2.1 NBS that are NEB

New European Bauhaus (NEB) tools and principles present three key values, i.e., **sustainability, beauty and inclusiveness** (co-creating together) that are independent spheres which need to be fulfilled on some level for a project or solution to be NEB, and as a working principle between the three values. This perspective is relevant for portraying their individual importance and for giving clear principles for developing their applications further, though they are clearly interconnected and influence one another.

Our NBS mapping generally highlighted the interconnected dynamics between the NEB values (i.e., **sustainability, inclusivity, beauty**), which affects the long-term success of the solutions (see [Section 4.3](#)). Genuine co-benefits seemed to emerge in situations when all three values align - but to get to that position, the mapping highlighted that ongoing processes of regenerating new understandings of sustainability, appropriateness, aesthetics and fairness needed constant collaboration between local communities and multidisciplinary stakeholders, and also an awareness of the possible tensions between the values.

Furthermore, the NEB encompasses **working principles** centred around **participatory processes, transdisciplinary approaches** and **multi-level engagement** which present three ambition levels for dealing with diverse stakeholders ([European Union, 2022](#)). As such, a full NEB project needs to contain all three values and working principles on some level, and in order to reach the highest ambition level it is required to address the challenges that have arisen on the lower levels ([European Union, 2022](#)).

Despite this, while the project descriptions in the NEB Compass ([European Union, 2022](#)) took a stance on conflicts and challenges at the global level (such as the climate crisis and increasing inequalities), and celebrated the positive potentials (or NEB to address these challenges), we found that they mainly gave examples of successful experiences and solutions, leaving out any lessons of potential internal tensions encountered in the projects. Thus, concrete ways of dealing with such challenges as part of the NEB working principles largely remained as unwritten tacit knowledge.

In relation to achieving long term sustainability and the wider application of NBS solutions that aid local ecosystems and generate additional value, the mapped NBS sources confirmed that this relied on **tackling emerging challenges together and co-creating a shared understanding of the co-benefits with different parties**. Generally, it was also found that perceived beauty of solutions dynamically altered in relation to individual needs and having access to, and agency related to the NBS. It was found that co-creating equal and fair solutions is dependent on the differences in perceptions, and on the environmental conditions that are created for diverse communities. See [Table 3](#) for examples of interconnections and tensions between co-benefits, tensions and solutions in relation to the three NEB values.

Table 2. Summary box with lessons for INNATURE to ensure NEB values are included

Based on this mapping, the forthcoming co-creation in the INNATURE pilot cases will place **anticipation, expectations and flexibility** towards potential emerging tensions as an additional tool to supplement the NEB working principles.

This means focusing on the collaboration methods that will be tested and co-developed for (and in) the INNATURE Eco-Social Living Labs (WP2) supported by Arts Conversations (WP3) as well as the monitoring methods that follow the implementation from ecological and social perspectives (WP4).

Table 3. Examples that highlight the interconnections between co-benefits, tensions and solutions in relation to the three NEB values. More detail and discussion in [Section 4.3](#).

NBS-NEB EXAMPLES	Interconnecting co-benefits, tensions and solutions
Sustainable	While the most effective measures for carbon sequestration are related to non-urban areas like agriculture and forests, human actions related to urban nature and soil can also increase carbon sinks, but they can as well cause additional emissions. As a solution to maximise co-benefits and minimise tensions (disbenefits), guidelines for easy to deliver and affordable actions to support carbon sinks in urban areas can give people agency and a stronger understanding of the impacts of their own actions on biodiversity and human & non-human health.
Together	Recognition of often excluded diverse values and local priorities enables biodiversity and wellbeing to be supported by doing this together, instead of top-down in local communities. This means engagement with commonly excluded groups in activities that connect people to places, communities and new imaginaries and this increases environmental justice.
Beautiful	Perceived beauty is dependent on people’s agency and access to NBS, but also on their everyday life situations. Co-creating appealing NBS solutions with the community in a way that address their daily needs can help to overcome prejudices and create acceptance and ownership to urban nature.

2.2.2 Transferability to INNATURE demo case contexts

This theme focuses on the transferability of findings to the specific INNATURE demo cases in the five European cities (i.e., Antwerp, Brezoi, Copenhagen, Sheffield and Tampere). In general, transferability of an innovation from its specific location to a new location was regarded as very challenging. There are variables such as changing political landscapes and people driving the implementation that often impact the orientation of NBS, hence the local contextualisation becomes a delicate matter. This was visible in most of the sources studied and it guided our mapping to understand and learn more about the applied *processes and practices* of how certain innovations were undertaken and implemented, instead of what they exactly were in specific detail. Reflections are listed in

[Table 4](#), with demo-case transferability examples listed in [Table 5](#) and more detail on each demo-case in [Section 4.4](#)

Table 4. Transferability lessons summary box

In relation to potentials of transferability to the INNATURE project in general, two clear themes were found. The first deals with innovations that **strengthen citizens’ connection to nature** and the second recognises potentials residing in **building the stakeholder network**. For strengthening citizens’ nature connections, visualising something formerly unnoticed, **supported by arts-based or narrative methods** and **embedded in the practical doing of things** were considered as central. In building a stakeholder network, it was found to be crucial to **allocate time, find mutual interests and embed the innovation beyond project timelines and actor groups**.

Table 5. Examples of transferable innovations to INNATURE demo case contexts; see [Section 4.4](#) for more.

TAMPERE POLLINATOR MEADOWS	ANTWERP GREEN STREET DELTA	BREZOI FOREST CLASSROOMS	COPENHAGEN RAIN COMMONS	SHEFFIELD LANDSCAPE CONNECTOR
Experimenting co-creative practices with non-humans (here a moth species)	Applying new design principles to significantly add vegetation to a dense urban structure	Developing a participatory forest coaching practice, adapted to climate change with low tech NBS methods	Multifunctional design to integrate sectors and actors, as well as to multiply resources	Exploring synergies in the landscape and local community at different scales

2.2.3 Scalability to other contexts

Common themes of **contextuality, continuity and mainstreaming, and engagement** were identified to create the most significant potential and restrictions for scalability and long-term resilience of NBS innovations (see [Section 4.5](#)). Contextuality in relation to identification of genuinely scalable (or non-scalable) solutions is crucial for upscaling to other contexts. The suitability to transfer to a given context should always be assessed carefully when upscaling NBS. From the studied resources, **we found that most of the actual solutions don't scale up directly but require de- and re-contextualising to identify the scalable part of the solution.** In many of the mapped cases, the method (such as e.g., planting trees), was often considered more generally scalable, though the actual solution, such as specific species or identification of possible locations, was bound to contexts.

Many potentials and restrictions for upscaling and long-term resilience of NBS were related to **continuity and mainstreaming** and is closely related to governance and decision-making processes. This emerged mostly when considering scalability of solutions at the city scale though it was also present at other scales. A significant potential **opportunity was observed in connection to official and formal adaptation of NBS and the integration of NBS and NEB values into urban planning.** An equally large **barrier to the upscaling of NBS was found to not being able to integrate and mainstream NBS into policymaking, and thus failing to ensure continued funding and responsibility.**

Potentials and restrictions related to **engagement, dissemination and language** were highlighted both as issues related to specific scales and as relevant for all scales. Engagement was considered crucial for gaining public acceptance and creating ownership and local meaning of solutions among diverse stakeholders. Successful implementation and long-term resilience of solutions as well as the success of their follow-up was found to rely on public acceptance and ownership. Scalability was also often considered to rely on effective translation of knowledge into accessible guidance. See [Section 4.5](#) for more detail about opportunities and barriers for upscaling NBS at the global, European, regional, city, neighbourhood and landscape scales.

3. Data collection and analyses methods

3.1 Project, case and literature mapping

As the aim of this deliverable is to learn from successful global and local NBS and NEB projects and research for the INNATURE NBS that are NEB-by-Design, we started with a co-created three-staged research strategy as unfolded below.

1. We systemically went through all projects of the [Network Nature reservoir](#), collecting those that were the most relevant for INNATURE. NetworkNature clusters and connects more than 100 EU-funded NBS research and innovation projects, including Horizon 2020 and EU Mission initiatives. Focusing on this extensive reservoir offered us a thorough view on NBS related research in Europe, given that Network Nature is the key NBS community. This also allowed us to highlight potential projects to connect with as part of **clustering activities** - see [Section 4.5.3](#).
2. To set our research in a global context, we studied recent reports such as ‘The Nature Global Roadmap on Urban Nature-Based Solutions: European Report’ (Kato-Huerta et al., 2025) that positions the European situation through high quality and extensive research carried out over 3 years. Altogether, this created the base collection of around 50 relevant projects, with their cases and related key literature.
3. To find the local NBS and NEB hidden gems, we enriched this data set with other sources by asking all researchers of the INNATURE consortium to add 5-10 cases or key sources from their local context or professional field that they found relevant to INNATURE, in addition to what we had already listed. Lastly, these project, case and literature listings were enriched by further searching the internet with keywords such as NBS and Nature-Based Solutions, offering us some interesting sources that were not so far listed. For example, this search included exploring [Urban Nature Atlas](#), a comprehensive database of NBS for cities.

Figure 2. Mapping investigated successful NBS and NEB projects. Photo from ØsterGro in Copenhagen. Photo: Elina Alatalo.

Overall, this resulted in 100 listings, of which most were research projects or case studies; research articles were also listed, either as a primary source or in connection to the project or case found. While the focus of our mapping was not concentrated on theory, through several of the cases and their innovations, theoretical aspects also strongly emerged, which can be seen in our synthesis.

For a more detailed study and to enable the extraction of foundational knowledge and key lessons learned from our 100 listings, they were divided amongst the INNATURE partners. This detailed study was guided by an Excel spreadsheet (see [Figure 3](#)) and by responding to questions in it and as set out in the initial task description and aim (T1.1.) of the INNATURE project. These were further co-developed and piloted; this process ensured that the key points of our mapping and what we wanted to learn, were covered. These key questions were as follows:

1. Resource title, online link and resource type
2. Reflection on lessons learned and key takeaways? (related to innovations, methods, approaches, successes, barriers, unintended consequences etc)
3. Description of any user / community engagement and in what way they were engaged?
4. Listing of innovative / notable NBS and NEB characteristics (inclusive, sustainable beautiful).
5. Any other reflections on e.g. transferability, scalability, long term resilience, maintenance/care, stakeholders etc.

WP1 researchers with TAU as task lead were responsible for most of this more detailed study. However, it was crucial to get a diverse group of researchers (altogether 13) from all of the INNATURE countries to undertake the mapping to ensure local and interdisciplinary expertise, knowledge and perspectives were shared and built-on. This was also crucial for the next stage of the study; i.e., to contribute different perspectives in the synthesis workshoping phase as a foundation for the co-creation of the overall detailed analysis of the entire data base and the emergence of key lessons and knowledge coming out of it - as unfolded below in [Section 3.2.](#)

Resource Title	Online link to main source	Resource type	Reflection on lessons learned and key takeaways? (related to innovations, methods, approaches, successes, barriers, unintended consequences etc)	Describe any user / community engagement and in what way were they engaged?	List innovative / notable NBS and NEB characteristics (inclusive, sustainable beautiful).	Any other reflections, e.g. transferability, scalability, long term resilience, maintenance/care, stakeholders etc.	Anything else
Guidelines for Urban Greening	https://www.urbangreening.eu/	Tool	Urban greening is a key element in the transition to a green and resilient city. It is essential to ensure that urban greening is implemented in a way that is inclusive, sustainable and resilient. This document provides a set of guidelines for urban greening in cities.	Urban greening is a key element in the transition to a green and resilient city. It is essential to ensure that urban greening is implemented in a way that is inclusive, sustainable and resilient. This document provides a set of guidelines for urban greening in cities.	Urban greening is a key element in the transition to a green and resilient city. It is essential to ensure that urban greening is implemented in a way that is inclusive, sustainable and resilient. This document provides a set of guidelines for urban greening in cities.	Urban greening is a key element in the transition to a green and resilient city. It is essential to ensure that urban greening is implemented in a way that is inclusive, sustainable and resilient. This document provides a set of guidelines for urban greening in cities.	
French case of the air relation to living well approach	https://www.urbangreening.eu/	Video recording	Urban greening is a key element in the transition to a green and resilient city. It is essential to ensure that urban greening is implemented in a way that is inclusive, sustainable and resilient. This document provides a set of guidelines for urban greening in cities.	Urban greening is a key element in the transition to a green and resilient city. It is essential to ensure that urban greening is implemented in a way that is inclusive, sustainable and resilient. This document provides a set of guidelines for urban greening in cities.	Urban greening is a key element in the transition to a green and resilient city. It is essential to ensure that urban greening is implemented in a way that is inclusive, sustainable and resilient. This document provides a set of guidelines for urban greening in cities.	Urban greening is a key element in the transition to a green and resilient city. It is essential to ensure that urban greening is implemented in a way that is inclusive, sustainable and resilient. This document provides a set of guidelines for urban greening in cities.	
One of the projects of a French urban greening approach	https://www.urbangreening.eu/	Case study website	Urban greening is a key element in the transition to a green and resilient city. It is essential to ensure that urban greening is implemented in a way that is inclusive, sustainable and resilient. This document provides a set of guidelines for urban greening in cities.	Urban greening is a key element in the transition to a green and resilient city. It is essential to ensure that urban greening is implemented in a way that is inclusive, sustainable and resilient. This document provides a set of guidelines for urban greening in cities.	Urban greening is a key element in the transition to a green and resilient city. It is essential to ensure that urban greening is implemented in a way that is inclusive, sustainable and resilient. This document provides a set of guidelines for urban greening in cities.	Urban greening is a key element in the transition to a green and resilient city. It is essential to ensure that urban greening is implemented in a way that is inclusive, sustainable and resilient. This document provides a set of guidelines for urban greening in cities.	
Artiles project	https://www.urbangreening.eu/	Project	Urban greening is a key element in the transition to a green and resilient city. It is essential to ensure that urban greening is implemented in a way that is inclusive, sustainable and resilient. This document provides a set of guidelines for urban greening in cities.	Urban greening is a key element in the transition to a green and resilient city. It is essential to ensure that urban greening is implemented in a way that is inclusive, sustainable and resilient. This document provides a set of guidelines for urban greening in cities.	Urban greening is a key element in the transition to a green and resilient city. It is essential to ensure that urban greening is implemented in a way that is inclusive, sustainable and resilient. This document provides a set of guidelines for urban greening in cities.	Urban greening is a key element in the transition to a green and resilient city. It is essential to ensure that urban greening is implemented in a way that is inclusive, sustainable and resilient. This document provides a set of guidelines for urban greening in cities.	
Coastline project	https://www.urbangreening.eu/	Project	Urban greening is a key element in the transition to a green and resilient city. It is essential to ensure that urban greening is implemented in a way that is inclusive, sustainable and resilient. This document provides a set of guidelines for urban greening in cities.	Urban greening is a key element in the transition to a green and resilient city. It is essential to ensure that urban greening is implemented in a way that is inclusive, sustainable and resilient. This document provides a set of guidelines for urban greening in cities.	Urban greening is a key element in the transition to a green and resilient city. It is essential to ensure that urban greening is implemented in a way that is inclusive, sustainable and resilient. This document provides a set of guidelines for urban greening in cities.	Urban greening is a key element in the transition to a green and resilient city. It is essential to ensure that urban greening is implemented in a way that is inclusive, sustainable and resilient. This document provides a set of guidelines for urban greening in cities.	
AVO project	https://www.urbangreening.eu/	Project	Urban greening is a key element in the transition to a green and resilient city. It is essential to ensure that urban greening is implemented in a way that is inclusive, sustainable and resilient. This document provides a set of guidelines for urban greening in cities.	Urban greening is a key element in the transition to a green and resilient city. It is essential to ensure that urban greening is implemented in a way that is inclusive, sustainable and resilient. This document provides a set of guidelines for urban greening in cities.	Urban greening is a key element in the transition to a green and resilient city. It is essential to ensure that urban greening is implemented in a way that is inclusive, sustainable and resilient. This document provides a set of guidelines for urban greening in cities.	Urban greening is a key element in the transition to a green and resilient city. It is essential to ensure that urban greening is implemented in a way that is inclusive, sustainable and resilient. This document provides a set of guidelines for urban greening in cities.	
CC CARBON urban tree methods and tree survey tool	https://www.urbangreening.eu/	Tool	Urban greening is a key element in the transition to a green and resilient city. It is essential to ensure that urban greening is implemented in a way that is inclusive, sustainable and resilient. This document provides a set of guidelines for urban greening in cities.	Urban greening is a key element in the transition to a green and resilient city. It is essential to ensure that urban greening is implemented in a way that is inclusive, sustainable and resilient. This document provides a set of guidelines for urban greening in cities.	Urban greening is a key element in the transition to a green and resilient city. It is essential to ensure that urban greening is implemented in a way that is inclusive, sustainable and resilient. This document provides a set of guidelines for urban greening in cities.	Urban greening is a key element in the transition to a green and resilient city. It is essential to ensure that urban greening is implemented in a way that is inclusive, sustainable and resilient. This document provides a set of guidelines for urban greening in cities.	

Figure 3. Extract of the of the Excel mapping dataset. A full list of the 100 resources is shared in Appendix 6.1 and the full Excel spreadsheet is shared as an Open Access data set on the [Zenodo INNATURE community website.](#)

3.2 Synthesis workshop

A three-hour online workshop, aided by an online whiteboard tool, invited together all researchers who had done the more detailed study, as well as other INNATURE project researcher who in general have vast knowledge of and NBS and NEB values. This group of 16 people worked on three mapping themes, following the learning café method - see [Figure 4](#). Theme 1 focused on **NBS innovations evaluated through NEB values**; Theme 2 tracked the issues of **transferability to INNATURE demo-cases**; and Theme 3 discussed aspects of **scalability and future application and resilience**. Qualitative content analysis was undertaken for each of these three themes on the whiteboard by the key WP 1 researchers.

The aim was to critically think further about these initially emerging findings within these themes; to find patterns and to understand what the findings point to as a whole. More resources were highlighted in the workshop and are referenced in this document separately from the initial data base. After the workshop, all researchers were given some post-workshop time to add to the whiteboard themes, with around 20 researchers contributing. The joint discussion at the end worked as a start of the final synthesis, as described below.

Figure 4. Whiteboards were used as platforms for workshoping. They served for the thematic grouping (NBS and NEB; Transferability to INNATURE, and scalability and future long-term resilience), and enrichment of discussions, acting as foundations to conclusions.

3.3 Synthesis

From the joint discussions in the workshop, some of the conclusions and lessons learned were already distilled and highlighted, which formed the starting point of the discussions and were further adjusted and refined in the workshop. Next, the key researchers working for WP1 deepened and diversified the workshop results by once more going through the detailed Excel listings and discussing them in a smaller group and bringing notes from the database and further reflections to complement the whiteboard. **The detailed learnings presented in this report are based on all the above processes.**

4. What we learned in more detail

4.1 State of the Art

For us, the state of the art of successful NBS and NEB projects became visible as we zoomed out from single solutions. It is difficult to transfer solutions from one context to another due to diverse ecological, cultural, political or climate related conditions. However, there are valuable learnings related to the *processes, methods, and practices as well as concepts developed* to understand what was taking place in the cases. This guided our synthesis to the larger scale issues.

Looking holistically at the results of the mapping, we found clear signs but also more subtle signs and suggestions of ongoing paradigm changes related to NBS. In the following, we outline these emerging new trends.

Firstly, **multifunctionality of the NBS** was referred to as the NBS answering several problems or producing many benefits at once, to varied stakeholders. Multifunctionality was found to be improved by design. This was often explored in connection to **systems thinking**, where solutions are not seen as separate, but as parts of nested systems at different scales, in which the interconnectedness of diverse solutions, stakeholders, activities, needs and perceptions are important to be understood. Here **regenerative design** acts as the approach that pursues the potential positive effects humans can have on urban nature.

Figure 5. Former industrial sites can be turned into multifunctional places for people and other species, such as the case of the Extraordinary Garden in Nantes. Photo: Elina Alatalo.

Next, from the sources it became clear that to act with urban nature, the capacity to *act with the unknown* is required, to allow for the dynamic and self-organised processes in natural environments, and to acknowledge that humans ultimately cannot control nature. For this, a plurality of co-creative methods were under development. These methods were also found to be purposeful when acting with citizen self-organisation. In the context of citizen engagement, ways to **act with plurality** were also experimented with, promising future practices for maintaining agencies with diverse views.

The sources additionally highlighted that we are also currently **unlearning human centrism** to gain multi-species actions and aspects in our cities. This is not limited to non-human animals or plants but also includes natural elements such as water streams and soil structures. Emerging approaches include e.g. **water-sensitive urban design** or a **living soil approach** that understand the connectivity of all human and non-human needs and actions, linking back to systems thinking.

Finally, **relational practices** that take the whole of human relations and their social context into account emerged in the context of NBS in two ways. First, the beauty of NBS was increasingly being experienced through learning about - and relating to - **a new approach and attitude to nature**. Second, it appeared that the social context became amplified through a **low-tech co-building** branch of NBS. Both the aesthetics and making of NBS were sometimes **gamified** in multiple ways to enrich participation.

These state-of-the-art findings of successful NBS and NEB projects framed out some of the associated research gaps that we synthesised, as presented in the following section.

4.2 Research gaps

At a general level the observed research gaps were linked to above mentioned paradigm changes. Based on the studied sources, there appeared a need for further knowledge related to emerging NBS approaches. This can be divided into three main categories:

1. We need more knowledge to better understand the ecological processes and aspects at **the in-use and operation stage of the NBS**, e.g. in a multifunctional NBS, but also to gain better practices in how to implement them. This key knowledge gap relates to **how NBS work over time**, as long-term monitoring is still scarce (Mahmoud, I., Morello, E., 2021, Dumitru, A., Frantzeskaki, N., & Collier, M., 2020) and there are also significant uncertainties in how local climates will develop in the future and hence how NBS will perform over time ([Urban Nature-Based Solutions: European report](#)). Hence the knowledge on how to design NBS systems that survive in a changing climate and during extreme weather events, alongside pinpointing the **possibilities for regenerative design**, such as supporting soil improvement processes, will be crucial.
2. Another knowledge gap was found to be on the **evolution of collaborative methods**, especially more cases are needed that explore how to support the changing attitudes of human and non-human relations and those that provide a more versatile testbed with different ecological, social, political and cultural conditions. Bridging this knowledge gap is necessary to enable critical consideration of the equity issues

between individual and societal needs of stakeholders and natural ecosystems. We found that cases were Europe focused, creating potential global knowledge gaps. Related to this is knowledge to be able to act in the **different temporalities** of NBS and people. This is highlighted by a need to develop practices and approaches that enable coordination between slow(er) processes related to nature and community commitment but that are also able to grasp the sudden, faster-paced moments of citizen engagement, as well as potential quick changes in city administration or the economy. For example, the benefits that urban nature can provide can take years to develop, however, this should not prevent the development of co-creative pilots and testbeds that allow collaborative learning in more agile or temporary ways.

3. A topic that rose up in the **scalability discussion** was the gap between NBS projects and **issues with their mainstreaming** at the same or other scales. Based on the studied sources, it was highlighted how that the solutions developed and implemented in the projects did not seem to become mainstream. This is further unfolded in [Section 2.2.3](#) and [4.5](#).

In summary, these three different research gaps are also closely interconnected. It was found that in order to unlearn human centrisms and to reach mind-changing future living imaginaries, new interdisciplinary knowledge of the **interconnections between sustainable ecosystems, human and non-human agency and perceived beauty** need to be developed together. For example, acknowledgement of the perspectives of a river, the active role wild animals like beavers can have in restoring its water quality and aquatic habitats, need not only novel administrative approaches, but also collaborative knowledge production with local communities and upscaling elsewhere.

These research gaps form a starting point to be further developed and to attempt to bridge them in the creation of the INNATURE NBS that are NEB-by-design, from which further reflections and lessons learned will be crystallised in the INNATURE Pattern Book at the end of the project.

Figure 6. The Alusta pavilion in Helsinki, Finland (2022). Designed by Suomi Koivisto architects with both human and non-human perspectives, co-produced with diverse local stakeholders and challenging perceptions of beauty. Photo: Sofie Pelsmakers

4.3 Learning from existing NBS that are NEB

Figure 7. The three NEB values: sustainable, beautiful, together (inclusivity)

As highlighted in [Figure 7](#), the New European Bauhaus (NEB) initiative focuses on the green transition in urban environments through **three values**: **sustainability** (addressing climate goals, circularity, zero pollution and biodiversity); **inclusivity** (valuing diversity and equality as well as accessibility and affordability for all); and **beauty** (focusing on aesthetics and the quality and local meaningfulness of experiences related not only to the environment but also related to practices and processes) ([European Union 2022](#)). The aim is to engage people at a neighbourhood grassroots level and prioritise social well-being.

In the INNATURE NBS mapping, the aim was to study how the NEB values were realised in the mapped cases. Based on the researchers' previous experience, the initial assumption was that NEB would not be explicitly present or mentioned and that all the underlying values as described would not be equally present in each case and that there was likely to be tensions between the values. The mapping was therefore structured around a search for co-benefits and tensions between the three values and solutions that were used for alleviating or solving the observed tensions.

A key finding from the mapping was that there was plurality in approaches and that while some cases highlighted one of the NEB values over others, sometimes other values were also materialised (whether intentionally or naturally developed). However, in other cases where priorities were one-sided, there were potentially overlooked connections and resulting tensions between the NEB values. Partially this related to the fact that the above-described NEB principles were not the starting point in most NBS cases. For example, NBS cases were found to mainly focus on regenerating biodiversity in certain aspects that may have encountered difficulties in reaching wider acceptability by citizens or decision-makers and therefore may represent tensions in relation to beauty or inclusion, which were not considered in the NBS creation.

On the other hand, the mapping also highlighted that such tensions and potential shortcomings could still appear even after careful consideration of all values. Therefore, awareness or mindfulness towards potential tensions, and flexibility of the process to take them into account is necessary.

Each of the three NEB themes as found in the mapping are further discussed below with overall 11 key themes identified as mapped in Tables 6 to 16. We discuss here the key findings of the mapped NBS sources through the overlapping lenses of the three NEB values of sustainability, beauty and inclusivity ('together'). Names and links to the relevant studied projects and cases are provided for further information and are summarised in the Excel dataset as found on the [Zenodo INNATURE community website](#).

4.3.1 Sustainable

Sustainability was found to be the core value in all NBS mapped. In NEB principles, sustainability was viewed mainly as characteristics of the environment, leaving aspects of economic or social sustainability as a focus of the other two NEB values. The different ambition levels defined for sustainability in the NEB compass ([European Union 2022](#)) illustrates ways of repurposing solutions to avoid or reduce environmental impacts, closing the loop towards circular processes, and regenerating solutions that not only reduce harm but create benefits to the environment.

The mapping displayed a variety of ecological and sustainability benefits for nature, urban environments and human and non-human species who live there. Mapped NBS solutions included actions related to carbon sequestration, soil health, urban vegetation and stormwater management, which created joint benefits for climate change adaptation, local biodiversity, and health and wellbeing.

Observed **challenges and tensions** within sustainability were found to be related in large part to knowledge gaps and insufficient understanding both of academic, administrative and public audiences. For example, the relevance of the cooling effect created by street vegetation had not been sufficiently recognised in Northern cities, and therefore it has remained under-researched and underutilised in urban design (e.g., [CoolGreen](#)). Likewise for understanding of the importance of soil, both as a carbon sink and as a healthy soil with its microbiome, which creates benefits for the human immune system, and how these can be considered in planning, seemed to only just being developed (see e.g., [CO-CARBON](#), [Carbon Gardening](#), [Maaperälähtöinen suunnittelu](#), [KOTA](#)). Developing a deeper understanding on these matters in the future creates potential for a paradigm shift towards deeper sustainability implementation and understanding of NBS co-benefits and their performance.

A summary is provided in the following tables related to the sustainability NBS benefits highlighted in the mapping, along four key themes: **carbon sequestration, urban greening/cooling, soil health and water management**. For each, identified co-benefits, tensions, solutions and key example sources (projects/cases) are provided - see Tables 6 to 9.

Table 6. Summary of carbon sequestration benefits, solutions and tensions as found in the studied sources, with key reference projects/cases.

CARBON SEQUESTRATION	
Identified co-benefits:	Parks, meadows, gardens, street plantings and most significantly soils can sequester carbon. Simple and affordable measures can simultaneously promote carbon sequestration and other well-being benefits.
Tensions:	Though non-urban agricultural and forest areas play a bigger role in carbon sequestration, the role of urban nature and human actions in it are also significant. Human actions affect urban nature a lot, for example a grass area may be a carbon sink or an emission. People do not consider urban nature as a potential carbon sink. The comparison of emissions of a building and the sink potential of its yard does not work, the scale is different.
Solutions:	It is relevant to consider what makes the yard a sink and not a source of carbon. This means: keep existing green; design new green carbon sinks; pay attention to low-emission construction and maintenance. Guidelines help people to act in their own everyday life for the health and biodiversity of their yards and create understanding of the role of sustainable environmental habits.
Key exemplary sources / projects:	
CO-CARBON , Carbon Gardening	

Table 7. Summary of urban green cooling benefits, solutions and tensions as found in the studied sources, with key reference projects/cases.

URBAN GREEN COOLING	
Identified co-benefits:	The urban heat island (UHI) effect and the role of trees is relevant also in Northern contexts. The temperature difference between a park and the built environment varies between 0.5-2 degrees (Jansson et al, 2007, Schwaab, J., et al., 2021). The choice of tree species matters to achieve the cooling effect (Bäcklin, O., (2025).
Tensions:	There is lack of research of heat island effect in Northern cities / the issue not getting enough attention in planning.
Solutions:	Gaining sufficient knowledge on UHI requires long-term monitoring in different local circumstances. On the other hand, testing cooling effects through local testbed solutions can help to gain knowledge of the local environment and place characteristics (intense monitoring of soil, water, wind, geographics, greenery), and can feed directly into more permanent or larger scale solutions, and similarly engage citizen into the process.
Key exemplary sources / projects:	
CoolGreen , Jubileumsparken	

Table 8. Summary of soil health benefits, solutions and tensions as found in the studied sources, with key reference projects/cases.

SOIL HEALTH	
Identified co-benefits:	Healthy soil is the basis of life. This aspect needs to be highlighted in agriculture and the significant importance of healthy farmlands as crucial in relation to the global soil health challenge. An important yet more minor role exists in the often more condensed sites of urban nature. We need to keep soil contact (permeability) possible and avoid moving masses of soil around. Growing media such as peat should not be used or brought from outside the city. When building, old soil with local biome communities should be kept on site. Soil needs to be thought of as a networked ecosystem.
Tensions:	Greening with transferable materials like peat creates benefits for health, education and beauty (see e.g. Kota), but is not necessarily the most sustainable solution as it also has a large ecological and carbon impact.
Solutions:	National level guidelines of healthy soil are being formed for the EU soil strategy. We should be reviving the soil and people in the same process (like establishing a micro-forest to health care facilities and other spaces). Use of biobased fertiliser from manure and plants.
Key exemplary sources / projects:	
Kota , Maaperälähtöinen suunnittelu , Erillään katoamme , trans4num	

Table 9. Summary of water management benefits, solutions and tensions as found in the studied sources, with key reference projects/cases.

WATER MANAGEMENT	
Identified co-benefits:	Restorative hydrology projects improve local water management, freshwater quality and aquatic habitats (for example, beaver damming rivers with dead wood and stones or using Zuni Bowls) and NBS projects aim to manage stormwater with nature-based methods rather than pipe-based discharge and can be easy to understand for citizens (e.g. rain gardens, permeable pavements).
Tensions:	The solutions can be perceived as a medium of growth for parasites such as mosquitos and as elements preventing other uses of the area.
Solutions:	Communication through examples are important to create acceptance. Use of stormwater elements with integrated benefits or double programming (e.g. leisure functions before and after flood events).
Key exemplary sources / projects:	
IN-HABIT , Les techniques de restauration Low-Tech	

4.3.2 Together (inclusivity)

Solutions implemented in urban environments always involve different interests, expectations and goals of the city administration, implementers, users, and the wider urban public. The mapped NBS sources showed how any differences were discussed, coordinated and considered through various means of collaboration. Here, co-creation opened key opportunities, for example to reconcile conflicting needs and renew perceptions of beauty in nature. As such, co-creation was shown to be an instrumental consolidating role within the NEB value trinity. At the same time, the mapped sources illustrated that collaboration could also act as a source of tensions, even without the additional layers of other NEB values. This aspect was also suggested in the NEB compass by pointing out that the necessity of equal treatment and opportunities does not guarantee equal outcomes as such ([European Union 2022](#)). While the mapped cases illustrated a wide range of co-benefits of inclusive approaches, tensions and solutions related to co-creation processes, transdisciplinarity, environmental justice, administration and civic resistance and friction related to participation were also highlighted.

The mapped sources also underlined that in each context and situation, the focus needs to be placed *on the methods and processes* for reaching diverse groups, hearing their voices and breaking the differences in perceptions, as well as overcoming counterproductive administrative silos. It was found that to gain actual co-benefits for both human and non-human wellbeing, the framing of the participatory processes need new imagination of mutually supportive ways of life.

Six key aspects related to inclusivity were identified in the mapped sources and are: **slow processes; transdisciplinary collaboration; environmental justice; administration; civic resistance, and participation friction.** See Tables 10 to 15.

Table 10. Summary of slow processes and the benefits, solutions and tensions as found in the studied sources, with key reference projects/cases.

SLOW PROCESSES	
Identified co-benefits:	Biodiversity can be increased through public urban landscapes that look good all year round via resilient, functional and naturalistic planting that is low maintenance with high visual impact, and through processes of a very slow and incremental approach with the community on board for management-informed design. The knowledge that NBS are long-term endeavours allows for experimentation in methods. Taking an incremental approach can also be less risky for nature and allow for testing innovative ideas and learning from shared knowledge. Patience is needed: ideas can take a long time (decades) to grow and be successful.
Tensions:	Resident involvement as well as investments in economy can be more sporadic and fast-paced than the decades long processes of nature.
Solutions:	Operate with a long-lasting basic unit and embedded engagement
Key exemplary sources / projects:	
Grev to Green Sheffield , Manor Fields Park , Green Estate , OpSkaLAR	

Table 11. Summary of transdisciplinary collaboration benefits, solutions and tensions as found in the studied sources, with key reference projects/cases.

TRANSDISCIPLINARY COLLABORATION	
Identified co-benefits:	Transdisciplinary collaboration can lead to new ideas and inclusive methods. For example, illustrations of new urban nature typologies as characters (like cartoon characters) can help in communicating their differences in a memorable and beautiful way. The creation of urban nature typologies as a collaboration between landscape architects and biologists has allowed to develop the ‘metering’ of well-being of urban nature, as well as developing recommendations for the maintenance or how to improve the situation.
Tensions:	Different ‘languages’ and jargons’ make communication of NBS ideas challenging.
Solutions:	Reframing the narratives and reducing professional jargon: focusing on positive aspects and highlighting the benefits in terms that specific stakeholders understand to gain their support. Use of arts, visuals and other communication methods that are more inclusive and across disciplinary boundaries.
Key exemplary sources / projects:	
ARVO , Grey to Green Sheffield	

Table 12. Summary of environmental justice benefits, solutions and tensions as found in the studied sources, with key reference projects/cases.

ENVIRONMENTAL JUSTICE	
Identified co-benefits:	Environmental justice can be addressed by co-creating inclusive, accessible green spaces that promote a just scaling-up of NBS in deprived urban areas. Enabling multispecies equality between humans and other species supports adaptation to new ways of life that support mutual wellbeing.
Tensions:	Public participation is common, but genuine co-creation is rare. Nature can be framed in a narrow and instrumental level, and commonly excluded stakeholders, such as marginalised communities and migrants, are left persistently in that position. This prohibits that they have a positive view on the created NBS.
Solutions:	Greater recognition of diverse values in NBS co-creation. Successful interventions align with local priorities, cultural values, and everyday experiences. Ensure accessible paths, include heritage in design, people need to have a connection to the NBS. Equity-focused engagement to include marginalised groups. Make it a living-lab environment, ensuring potential for education, connecting to impact to ensure that no tensions arise. Unlearning through various engaging activities: a paradigm shift is required to unlearn the framework of human mastery over nature.
Key exemplary sources / projects:	
FairNature , Natura Global Roadmap , Network Nature , Les Tartres , ReWaM , euPOLIS , MUST	

Table 13. Summary of administrative processes and benefits, solutions and tensions as found in the studied sources, with key reference projects/cases.

ADMINISTRATION	
Identified co-benefits:	Nature-based solutions experiments that are built on trust between the city and its citizens support the aim of the experiment and the success of the experimenting process itself.
Tensions:	Administrative silos and limited long-term funding constrain uptake and can cause tensions between government and citizen. Sudden changes in place-making capital investments can cause ruptures for NBS processes. There is institutional friction embedding citizen-led processes into formal planning. There are land tenure complexities, regulatory approvals and bureaucratic constraints to be navigated.
Solutions:	Experimentation can be aided with both local and central governments allowing flexibility in terms of how their funding and programmes are implemented. Trust can be created by providing space for citizen actions in processes initiated by the city.
Key exemplary sources / projects:	
Resilient Europe , Manor Fields Park , Green Estate , Grey to Green Sheffield , REGREEN , Clevercities , RISE , Nekala	

Table 14. Summary of civic resistance and its benefits, solutions and tensions as found in the studied sources, with key reference projects/cases.

CIVIC RESISTANCE	
Identified co-benefits:	Civic resistance can bring the community together around a common goal to protect nature through protest action.
Tensions:	Tensions however arise when it places citizens and other stakeholders at opposite ends in a conflict. For example, when a council decided, on behalf of the city, to manage its urban tree population by removing 50% of the mature street trees and replacing them with young trees. The citizens strongly disagreed.
Solutions:	Partnership is possible after protest and requires more inclusive representation in bottom-up instead of top-down decision-making processes. For example, the decision-making around the city's street trees is no longer down to the council and its contractor. Instead, a citywide partnership is made up of representatives from the protest group, local charities, the city's two universities and independent advisors. There are street tree wardens who are volunteers who champion the trees in their local patch.
Key exemplary sources / projects:	
Sheffield Street Tree Partnership	

Table 15. Summary of friction in participation and its benefits, solutions and tensions as found in the studied sources, with key reference projects/cases.

PARTICIPATION FRICTION	
Identified co-benefits:	Citizens understand the value of their own time and care and want to contribute if it is meaningful to them. They want to find new ways of participation which are more meaningful to them and when embedded in different ways in citizens’ and communities’ lives.
Tensions:	Residents get tired of being engaged in researchers' projects. It is important to involve residents only when a clear mandate is available, i.e. what is in it for them and why are they needed for the solution. Also, a relevant timing of citizen participation is important: too early participation can cause frustration due to unclear, unfinalised plans.
Solutions:	Rather than approaching all residents at once, it may be better to approach already established communities. For example, a crucial practice was found when one crossroads became a dedicated place for a ‘Parliament’, where discussions on the pros and cons of the experiment were facilitated, as well as ideas further developed. User and community engagement became part of the ‘day-to-day’ domain.
Key exemplary sources / projects:	
OpSkaLAR , Barcelona Superblocks , Three Points Approach , GoGreenRoutes	

4.3.3 Beautiful

The concept of beauty is commonly related to visually harmonious or even traditional characteristics. The mapping of NEB solutions revealed that beauty is not attached to static ideas of qualities, but rather something that is dynamically changing, contested and adapted, learned and unlearned and is connected to local meaning.

Figure 8. Currently more wild and messy aesthetics of nature are becoming approved even in urban contexts. Photo from Copenhagen by Elina Alatalo.

The NBS mapping pointed out that beauty, as understood in the context of NEB, is always connected to other values. This is evident in all the ambition levels presented in the NEB compass ([European Union 2022](#)). For example, already at the lowest level, beauty is connected to activation of cultural, social and natural qualities and diversities of a place, placing focus also on sustainability and togetherness.

The mapped cases illustrated how at its best, beauty relied on novel understandings of sustainability; it was relational and co-created together with stakeholders and communities in an equal manner, taking their diverse needs into account, and giving them agency for - and access to - NBS.

On the other hand, the mapping also revealed that ideas of what is generally considered beautiful can be in tension with sustainability targets or there can be tensions between diverse stakeholders. Most of the identified tensions in the mapped cases related to the question of what is perceived and understood as beautiful or otherwise acceptable in urban environments. For example, people have learned to appreciate short lawns that look tidy in urban environments, but which are very poor from a biodiversity viewpoint. On the other hand, biodiverse environments such as a meadow may take several years to develop and are not necessarily considered beautiful by many, especially in the early, messy stages. Solutions to these tensions provided examples of how new understandings can be developed together. It is also important to note that in the name of understandable benefits for people, solutions might be made that are not necessarily the best for long-term sustainability in the local environment and these tensions need to be carefully managed.

Table 16. Summary of the interconnection between beauty, sustainability and inclusivity and benefits, solutions and tensions as found in the studied sources, with key reference projects/cases.

BEAUTY-SUSTAINABILITY-INCLUSIVITY INTERCONNECTION	
Identified co-benefits:	When NBS are legible, visible, and aesthetically integrated, they gain broader acceptance among planners, users, and decision-makers.
Tensions:	NBS can look ugly to the public, the solutions are not necessarily understood correctly, or they can even seem harmful for humans or nature. The perception of beauty depends also on its gained value.
Solutions:	To reimagine values and attitudes to beauty as related to NBS. Aesthetic appeal reimaged refers to: co-creation with users, designers, artists and architects as a strategy to generate appealing and socially acceptable NBS designs. Communication through examples and links with community traditions are important for the acceptance of NBS. Info panels and meetings to show the human benefit of respecting non-human agents in our habitats are needed. People are also happier with the NBS if it solves a real problem and generates value for their everyday needs (like avoiding increases in rent).
Key exemplary sources / projects:	
Green Climate Screen , Les techniques de restauration Low-Tech , IN-HABIT , OpSkaLAR , Augmented Urbans , Resilient Europe .	

4.4 Transferability

Figure 9. Diagram illustrating the transferability lessons learned to the INNATRE demo cases in Finland, Belgium, Denmark, Romania and the UK.

In this section we concentrate on answering the following questions: What studied innovations can be transferred and used in the INNATURE demo case locations? What are their potentials and uncertainties, as well as barriers to overcome? In addition to sharing informative examples of the transferable innovations, our focus has been on critical reflections on the findings of the mapping of the cases and projects especially related to transferability from one context to another.

4.4.1 General transferability to the INNATURE project

Transferability is highly contextual and local, and while specific NBS solutions may not apply elsewhere, we focused on general lessons learned and applicability across cases and projects and sources, always keeping the five INNATURE demo-cases' climatic, environmental, socio-demographic, and administrative contexts in mind.

In relation to the potentials of transferability to the INNATURE project, two clear themes were highlighted in the mapping of sources, where the INNATURE project can benefit: the first deals with **innovations that strengthen citizens' connection to nature** (see [Table 17](#)) and the second recognises **potentials residing in building the stakeholder network** (see [Table 18](#)). Then we focus on the general potential barriers and uncertainties of transferability (see

[Table 19](#)), followed by ideas for transferability in each demo-case location (see [Tables 20-24](#)).

Table 17. Summary of the general INNATURE lessons learned related to the potential in strengthening of citizen's connection to nature.

POTENTIALS IN STRENGTHENING CITIZENS' NATURE CONNECTION
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visualising something formerly invisible or easily misunderstood to citizens emerged strongly as an innovation in the mapping. These may be e.g. natural processes that are difficult to grasp, small species, or elements like a river. For example, revealing hidden natural beauty is found to engage citizens (e.g. Co-Carbon); storytelling to teach co-benefits and governance of nature (e.g., EcoAdvance), and an immersive multi-media cupola to help imagine multi-species justice in cities (e.g., MUST).
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Art in general is recognised as an excellent medium in mediating and sparking explorations of people's nature connection (e.g. Sleeping Beauty).
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrating AI may create groundbreaking interfaces to strengthen nature connections: imagine a possibility to talk with a blue whale (e.g., Nature Perspectives) or understanding the value of trees (e.g., TreesAI).
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In this context, citizens' creativity may also burst in unintended ways: for example, in Australia, when trees were given e-mail addresses for residents to report on their condition, people started to write love letters to them (ABC News). The River Don in Sheffield has received similar creative letters of affection.

Table 18. Summary of the general INNATURE lessons learned related to the potential in building the stakeholder network.

POTENTIALS IN BUILDING THE STAKEHOLDER NETWORK
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allocating plenty of time for building the stakeholder network is experienced as a potential, as it allows to try things and make mistakes together, growing trust between people (e.g., Manor Fields Park and Green Estate).
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When extending the network, potentials lie in noticing mutual interests, like including unemployed people (e.g., VERDIR) and spotting win-win possibilities, such as aligning grassroots place-attachment with city and water-board aims (e.g., Essenburgpark). These kinds of multi-benefit outcomes may be reached by shared understanding and durable stewardship (e.g., EcoAdvance).
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building a large city-wide coalition beyond the project itself (e.g., ReWET) creates potentials to embed practices such as co-creation (e.g., CLEVER Cities) and to integrate cross sectoral work in the long run (e.g., Augustenborg).
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Working and discussing around practical and concrete things was found appealing and inclusive. Informality of doing actions together creates platforms for different stakeholders to mix. For example, walking tours presenting NBS innovations to civil servants from different cities were highly popular (e.g., Nekala; Barcelona Superblocks). Similarly, low-tech solutions enable the actual physical building together (e.g., TERRRA).
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Giving citizens agency in new fields adds participation, such as making them ambassadors of metering (e.g., Curieuzeneuzen).

Table 19. Summary of the general INNATURE lessons learned related to uncertainties and barriers in the transferability of NBS innovations.

GENERAL CONCERNS RELATED TO TRANSFERABILITY OF NBS INNOVATIONS	
Uncertainties	A changing political landscape may impact the project orientation (e.g., Barcelona Superblocks ; Zografos, 2020). Translation into policy does not guarantee success. Even inside the city, as the context changes, the NBS innovation might not work so well, often because it is experienced by people as ‘imported to’ them (e.g., From Grey to Green ; Washbourne & Wansbury, 2023; Frago Clols & Graziano, 2021). Challenges arise when people who originated the innovation are not part of the translation or implementation of the idea anymore (e.g., Hiedanranta , Alatalo et al., 2025).
	Uncertainty can also be a positive thing, allowing iterative and open processes, where solutions are developed on a local testbed site to gain knowledge of the environment and place characteristics (e.g., Jubileumsparken).
Barriers	High upfront capital costs of some of the NBS innovations (e.g., RISE-IN ; ReWET)
	We should be aware of the relevant level and focus of co-creation. (Plüschke-Altöf et al., 2025)
	Multiplicity of levels involved in the project requires meaningful translation between European level goals, project goals, and local understandings of NBS and NEB values to ensure relevance as well as targeted and inclusive engagement with communities and project partners (e.g., Eco-Advance ; Månsson & Persson, 2021). Because the geographical differences in climate and soil, some NBS innovations are not functioning in other locations. However, this should not be used as an excuse to not adopt or apply something.

Figure 10. In transferability the local conditions may alter greatly, such as maintenance practices of cutting the lawn and weeding or letting things grow, as here in Copenhagen. Photo: Sofie Pelsmakers.

4.4.2 Transferability to Tampere, Finland

The INNATURE Demo Case 1 deals with meadow-like habitats in sub-urban areas in Tampere, Finland. Meadows will be implemented in two neighbourhoods (Nekala and Härmälänranta) with the aim to increase biodiversity and access to urban nature while developing gathering places for their residents. Special focus is on supporting an endangered moth species as well as pollinators.

Table 20. Transferability potential to the demo case in Tampere (Finland), based on key findings and lessons learned from the mapping.

TRANSFERABILITY TO TAMPERE, FINLAND	
Transferable potentials found in the mapping	It is possible to experiment with co-creative practices and arts-based visualisations with the community that increase citizen understanding of non-human species. This helps people to perceive and better understand and care for non-humans (e.g., Co-Evolvers , the loveletters for trees in Australia). Learning about biodiversity while doing is found to be effective, like learning about planted vegetation through an app on a phone. In-situ nature observation marathons with local experts can raise ownership of NBS objectives. (e.g., Augmented Urbans)
Uncertainties	The question of aesthetics is central in the Tampere case, as demonstrated by earlier Nekala meadows and the City Blues project. NBS meadows are initially ugly and take a long time to establish compared to non-NBS meadows. Aesthetic appeal can be reimaged and co-created (e.g., Resilient Europe), even if residents might at first critically assess NBS as elitist or lazily maintained (e.g., Augmented Urbans ; García Antúnez, 2024).
Barriers	The Nordic climate sets barriers to transfer some of the best practices to Tampere.

4.4.3 Transferability to Antwerp, Belgium

The NNATURE Demo Case 2 focuses on greening the streets of low-rise urban areas in Antwerp, Belgium, using a commons-based approach that fosters social cohesion and inclusion. Garden streets will be implemented in two clusters in the Borgerhout district, a densely built-up area with half the permeable surfaces and higher exposure to air pollution compared to the rest of the city. These green interventions create shared spaces where residents collectively care for their environment, strengthening community ties and neighbourhood well-being.

Figure 11. Example of the hard, impermeable and densely built-up area of the District of Borgerhout (left) vs the newly developed green and permeable surfaces of the Antwerpen-Zuid area (right). Photo: Sofie Pelsmakers

Table 21. Transferability potential to the demo case in Antwerp (Belgium), based on key findings and lessons learned from the mapping.

TRANSFERABILITY TO ANTWERP, BELGIUM	
Transferable potentials found in the mapping	Urban Green can be celebrated through new ways of engaging a diverse community, e.g., as a street festival, with information booths on NBS, art workshops, street food etc. (e.g., Berlin Baumscheibefest).
	A manifesto can talk about the importance of e.g. urban trees, and canopy cover atlas can show what the number of trees in the residents’ neighbourhoods is in relation to others (e.g., Co-Carbon).
	Even though the amount of vegetation tends to be low in dense urban areas there are several ways for significantly adding vegetation and multi-species wellbeing in these settings (e.g., JustTrees ; Hautamäki et al., 2024).
	Green corridors, gardens and other solutions have recently been realised in comparable scales in three cities: Hamburg, London and Milan (e.g., Clever Cities).
Uncertainties	The building sector needs to adapt their practices to e.g. establishment of micro-forests in the cities (e.g., Apart we shall perish).
	We can learn from a new policy in Vantaa, Finland: if you harm an urban tree you need to pay, depending on the damage, from 200 to 12 000 euros. This applies to construction firms and citizens alike. The process of creating the policy brought people from different departmental silos to discuss urban trees together. This created new local know-how and cleared earlier prejudices (see e.g., Vantaa Tree Policy). How the policy will work remains to be seen: the policy was put in place only in the beginning of September 2025.
Barriers	In planting 170 000 urban trees in Paris, it has been noted that many criteria from micro-climate to exposure, soil depth, street width, global warming, allergenic potential and maintenance need to be considered. To successfully combat urban heat islands, trees were not always found the best solutions, especially if the streets are too narrow. However, where successful, the results were amazing: with a 100 m distance, a difference of experienced heat can vary from the 33 degrees of the green street to 50 degrees of the grey street. Here the density of trees as well as the choice of tree species were crucial (see Plan Arbre).

4.4.4 Transferability to Brezoi, Romania

The INNATURE Demo Case 3 concentrates on forest classrooms in the urban and rural settings of Brezoi in Romania. The town of Brezoi includes several villages and is surrounded by mountains that are 70% covered by woodland that is for a large part managed as a traditional commons. The main objective is for the community to adopt new restorative practices and re-learn traditional ways of managing the forest. See [Table 22](#).

Table 22. Transferability potential to the demo case in Brezoi (Romania), based on key findings and lessons learned from the mapping.

TRANSFERABILITY TO BREZOI, ROMANIA	
Transferable potentials found in the mapping	Improving accessibility to nature (routes as well as information) has been found crucial. Accessibility provides possibilities for citizens to contextually understand the role and importance of nature and ecosystem services (e.g., Vanhankaupunginlahti, TreesAI).
	The method of Garden Coaching, where researchers together with garden owners develop better gardening practices in a relationship resembling a personal trainer, could be applied also to the forest context (e.g., Co-Carbon).
	Community woodland guidelines to share tools for engagement (e.g., Co-Evolvers) and involving marginalised groups (Roma, unemployed, women) in NBS co-creation (e.g., VERDIR).
	The idea of shared natural heritage to mobilise the role of local cultural understandings of sustainability and re-value existing traditional knowledge can be transferred (e.g., TRANS-lighthouses, Gammare collective , Reti et al., 2025)
	The forest, mountain rivers and woods have greater potential for experimenting with the co-creation of NBS related to forest, water management, geomorphic restoration, and urban design (e.g., TRANS-lighthouses, Network Nature, DesirMED).
Uncertainties	Small scale interventions are accessible for citizens to access and implement but require dedicated individuals willing to experiment. Having functioning co-produced prototypes can be an effective way to mobilise participation. For example, approaches such as restorative hydrology and castor techniques are easy for citizens to understand and require small budgets but require further experimenting (AAA). Similarly promising but still developing solutions are fog curtains to collect water and are easy to realise by participatory approaches that also support a future changing climate and long-term NBS resilience (AAA).
	Small scale interventions can be effective in improving biodiversity, soil quality and climate resilience, but how to scale them up to address local system-level issues remains. Brezoi town administration have a crucial role to play in scaling-up NBS in the city and to facilitate access to other administrative stakeholders (e.g. regional water company) (See also Eco-Advance).
Barriers	There are challenges in involving a community that is more concerned with economic issues (jobs, standard of living, etc.). This might be addressed by linking NBS goals with local economic goals, for example through financial incentives (e.g., IN-HABIT).
	Re-learning traditional local skills to activate a local network for implementing NBS requires revalorisation of traditional local skills, as well as translation between local and NEB values. Working around tangible results and improvements could be an effective way to demonstrate the value of traditional NBS techniques (See also Carbon Gardening).

4.4.5 Transferability to Copenhagen, Denmark

The INNATURE Demo Case 4 is about rain commons in a high-rise modernist social housing estate in urban Copenhagen, Denmark. The aim is to understand how NBS for stormwater management can mobilise large-scale systemic transitions in water infrastructure, replacing conventional costly and carbon intensive flood prevention solutions. Additionally, the rain commons include a permaculture community-garden, directly linking to stormwater through water harvesting schemes for irrigation, and indirectly through the overarching idea of exploiting water and nature as a resource for unfolding locally embedded NEB values.

Table 23. Transferability potential to the demo case in Copenhagen (Denmark), based on key findings and lessons learned from the mapping.

TRANSFERABILITY TO COPENHAGEN, DENMARK	
Transferable potentials found in the mapping	Traditional co-operatives are extending to include natural elements as key stakeholders. In Zoöp people make decisions together with plants, animals and e.g. water (e.g., DeCeuvél)
	Infrastructure projects can be centres for new ways of working together with citizens (Resilient Europe).
	Multifunctional design can integrate sectors (Augustenborg). As an example of multifunctionality, by removing concrete and asphalt in the city, rainwater can replenish groundwater, support the biodiversity and soil and provide greener social places for people (e.g., Plan Arbore). The Three Points Approach is a conceptual framework for urban flood risk and water management that supports climate change adaptation by integrating technical, spatial, and societal perspectives (Fratini et al., 2012).
Uncertainties	Vertical and freestanding NBS demonstrate that stormwater management does not have to rely solely on ground infiltration. This is particularly valuable in dense urban contexts with limited soil access, which aligns well with NEB’s ambition to rethink spatial constraints creatively (Lausen, Jensen, Randall, 2020).
	Though NBS is planned for flood prevention, it needs to thrive also in drought conditions (City Blues).
Barriers	Organisational silos in the local institutions, extended implementation timelines, long-term maintenance and reconciling short-term funding with long term project objectives have been found challenging (Augustenborg).
	The existing planning and water management frameworks that are designed around conventional solutions do not allow for innovative solutions. Freestanding or unconventional NBS may not fit into current standards, slowing approvals and funding (e.g., Opskalar).
	Technical NBS tools do not always align with the diverse local contexts (euPOLIS).

4.4.6 Transferability to Sheffield, UK

The INNATURE Demo Case 5 works with a Landscape Connector of peri-urban Sheffield in the UK. Connections will be developed in the Gleadless Valley, which is a 1950s-60s modernist housing estate built on hilly terrain, with a Local Nature Reserve and river nearby. Activities include enhancing biodiversity and ecosystems, strengthening the local agroecological food systems and supporting civic learning.

Table 24. Transferability potential to the demo case in Sheffield (UK), based on key findings and lessons learned from the mapping.

TRANSFERABILITY TO SHEFFIELD, UK	
Transferable potentials found in the mapping	Synergies arise when NBS innovations are thought of as systems in the landscape. One such system can comprise of multi-functional pocket parks and green corridors, urban waterways with biotope nodes and floating islands, rainwater run off management systems and retention basins, vertical green walls, roof gardens, and metabolic hubs, in connection with cultural urban hubs for art, education, and community interaction (e.g., euPOLIS).
	Paying attention to several scales and levels in this system is important, e.g., green and permeable parking and district gardens should be thought about at the district level, green roofs and rain gardens at the site level (e.g., Grow Green Modena).
	Taking inspiration from the Amsterdam urban planning guidelines for Living Soil (City of Amsterdam, 2021) to the peri-urban context, with inspiration from artist Lehmusruus 's practice with soil scientists and regenerative farmers as well as urban nature experts, all offer potentials for transfer.
Uncertainties	Ecological restoration is impacted by actions of other people in other locations, such as upstream activities beyond project control (e.g., ReWET).
	Working together with all sides of the community in different ways at different scales is challenging (e.g., Sheffield Street Tree Partnership ; Dempsey & Burton, 2012).
	Offering shorter procurement periods for environmentally oriented retrofitting projects may also lead to green washing (e.g., Augmented Urbans).
Barriers	Ignoring the emotional, cultural and social relationships that urban residents have with their landscape can bring lasting and politically damaging change (e.g., Sheffield Street Tree Partnership).
	The residents have been over-consulted in recent times. Gleadless Valley has been 'masterplanned' a couple of times now which has involved extensive consultation, but little by way of action and change, which is potentially damaging the trust between residents and the council (Plüschke-Altöf et al., 2025).

4.5 Future, scalability and long-term resilience

Figure 12. Diagram illustrating the consideration of NBS solutions and methods from landscape site to neighbourhood, city, region, country, European level and globally.

In the future, scalability and long-term resilience theme the mapped cases and projects were tested through the lenses of different scales. The aim was to highlight the potentials and restrictions of the identified solutions and methods, but also to explore emerging issues from the mapped cases from many different perspectives. The potentials and restrictions of these different scales were then studied to identify common themes from several perspectives, including lessons applicable to all scales (see [Section 4.5.9](#)). There is also a section on potential clustering possibilities with European projects - see [Section 4.5.3](#).

4.5.1 Global

Global scalability of NBS solutions and methods was found to have less potential and was more restricted. Easily adaptable justifications for NBS such as health benefits have potential to help solutions upscale globally. Potential scalability for NBS lies in globally vital practices such as agriculture. Technological tools and applications contain potential by reaching participants even globally. The importance of identifying the genuinely scalable solutions to prevent maladaptations was identified in the analysis.

Restrictions for global scalability related to knowledge pooling and gaps, tendency towards certain solutions, and complex terminology. At present, NBS research is Europe focused and leaves potential global knowledge gaps. Another research gap related to the lack of long-term resilience research. Moreover, NBS tend to gravitate towards stormwater management and biodiversity, at the expense of other themes such as carbon sinks. NBS based on building new or modifying existing infrastructure at a smaller scale dominated nature conservation projects that could have global scalability potential. More detail is unfolded in [Table 25](#).

Table 25. Summary of NBS / NEB innovations with global scalability potential

NBS / NEB INNOVATIONS WITH GLOBAL SCALABILITY POTENTIAL

- Coupling NBS with evidence of health benefits was seen as potentially scalable and fundable at the global scale ([RISE](#))
- NBS in agriculture such as biostimulants and minimum tillage for soil health, biobased fertiliser from organic waste to replace chemical fertilisers and reduce nitrate leaching or plant based nutrient management all have global scalability potential ([Trans4num](#)).
- Technology and applications were presented as potential tools to help solutions upscale globally.

Table 26. Restrictions and limitations of global scalability of NBS

RESTRICTIONS / LIMITATIONS (WHAT TO LOOK OUT FOR?)
<p>Main sources and examples from: The Natura Global Roadmap, Urban Nature-Based Solutions: European report</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As a cautionary (and ongoing) example of maladaptation, Miyawaki forest planting was discussed as a practice that has been adopted around the UK without enough background research of long-term resilience and adaptability to the local climate (Morales et al. 2026). • Most research is done in Europe and therefore shaping global discourse. All necessary global knowledge gaps may not be addressed. • A research gap for long-term resilience: it is unclear how co-benefits evolve when solutions age. • Some NBS themes dominate, e.g., biodiversity and storm water management dominate. • There is a dominance of creating new or modifying existing infrastructures instead of protecting larger ecosystems. • Non-uniform terminology: e.g. Ecosystem services and green infrastructure are other terms used instead of NBS.

Figure 13. Transformations of existing infrastructure provide plenty of possibilities to include NBS that also support social cohesion. Photo: Krista Willman.

4.5.2 Europe

At the European scale, the potential solutions related mostly to the modification of existing infrastructures. Identified methodical potentials related to upscaling by mainstreaming and feeding latest innovations into guidance and practice through suitable language. Language was also identified as a potential barrier for upscaling in Europe or in any international environment. Reaching crowds by ICT solutions such as games was highlighted as a big potential but can also potentially be very restrictive for marginalised users. [Table 27](#) and [Table 28](#) provide summaries.

Table 27. Summary of NBS / NEB innovations with European scalability potential

NBS / NEB INNOVATIONS WITH SCALABILITY POTENTIAL WITHIN EUROPE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Infrastructure transformation: Transformation of transport or old industrial infrastructure with NBS' has continental scalability potential (Essenburgpark). • Multi-stakeholder governance of municipalities, businesses and citizens was seen as essential for embedding the NBS into urban planning regulations and EU green transition strategies (Nature4cities). • A Europe wide multilingual survey and follow-up exchanges that brought in perspectives from scientists, managers, community organisers and policy actors, feeding directly into guidance. Engagement is also “translated” into practice via stakeholder-focused checklist. (EcoAdvance)

Table 28. Restrictions and limitations of European scalability of NBS

RESTRICTIONS / LIMITATIONS (WHAT TO LOOK OUT FOR?)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Language and cultural barriers are relevant for upscaling any multilingual project. Translating e.g. concepts may turn out very difficult. Paraphrasing concepts and ensuring that substance is not lost in translation is resource intensive. (Guidelines for carbonwise gardening) • Reaching large crowds by ICT solutions, games, augmented reality or wearable sensors is a big potential but including marginalised voices such as older people and immigrants is important. (EUropolis)

4.5.3 Clustering possibilities with EU funded projects

Our mapping started by going through the collection of EU-funded projects in the [NetworkNature online reservoir](#) and the lessons from these projects (and other) relevant for INNATURE are presented in this report. Finding synergies with other EU funded, or partly EU funded projects were also of particular interest for future potential clustering activities. Clustering with these projects, be it about continuing on their legacy or organising joint activities with the ongoing projects, holds a potential for deepening the learnings presented. Some of the most promising clustering possibilities for the future were identified and include the following ongoing projects:

- The [Spongeworks](#) project, ongoing until 2028, has contextual similarities with urban INNATURE cases highlighted in [Section 4.4](#).
- The [Sleeping Beauty](#) project (ongoing until 2029) recognises strengthening citizens’ nature connection through art ([Section 4.4](#)).
- The [URBREATH project](#) is in a similar phase to INNATURE. The URBREATH Tallinn pilot construction works are planned to begin in June 2026 URBREATH is also about developing decision making tools which are highlighted relevant for scalability in [Section 4.5](#).
- The [City Blues](#) project, ongoing until 2027, is contextually similar to the INNATURE Tampere case ([Section 4.4.2](#))
- The [LAND4CLIMATE](#) project, ongoing until 2027, has potentially relevant learnings on developing NBS on private land ([Section 4.5.7](#)).
- The [Coevolvers](#) project, ending 2026 is relevant due contextual similarities to the Tampere demo case as well as in how art is used as a medium in demo cases.

EU co-funded projects include:

- The [FairNature](#) project (2025-2028) has potential learnings about fair and equitable NBS processes ([Section 4.3.3](#)).
- The [Greenstorm](#) project (ongoing until 2026), has potential deeper learnings for adapting NBS by local authority engagement ([Section 4.5.6](#)).

Clustering possibilities will be explored more in detail in relation to the phases of INNATURE, starting e.g. with those that feed into the early stages of the demo cases, reaching towards dissemination and exploitation - see also the INNATURE Deliverable D7.1 (Communication, Dissemination and Clustering plan).

4.5.4 Country

Country specific NBS upscaling and long-term resilience in the studied projects mainly related to mainstreaming and the wider adoption of small-scale NBS. Mainstreaming and integrating NBS in planning were identified as important aspects for countrywide scalability. NBS in home gardens were an example of small-scale solutions with scalability potential through appropriate guidance to home owners - see [Table 29](#). Restrictions for upscaling countrywide NBS solutions was related to mainstreaming, if context was disregarded, or a lack of public acceptance caused by one way participation and potential issues with effective dissemination; [see Table 30](#).

Table 29. Summary of NBS / NEB innovations with country scalability potential

NBS / NEB INNOVATIONS WITH SCALABILITY POTENTIAL WITHIN A COUNTRY
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Getting scenario tools and ecosystem service modelling integrated in planning processes is a big potential for city or countrywide NBS upscaling. For example, ReGreen applied a toolkit that strengthened decision making and mainstreaming NBS into municipal policies (e.g., ReGreen, TreesAI). • Home gardens represent a vast amount of green space and have a lot of NBS scalability potential through guidance. Also scalable by developing guides for housing associations (e.g., Guidelines for carbonwise gardening).

Table 30. Restrictions and limitations of country scalability of NBS

RESTRICTIONS / LIMITATIONS (WHAT TO LOOK OUT FOR?)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experimental development often takes place in temporary developing places which can threaten long-term sustainability (e.g., De Ceuvel). • Guidelines may be ineffective even within a country with different climates and ecological niches. Ensuring de- and re-contextualisation of guidelines is crucial for countrywide or larger scale upscaling (e.g., Guidelines for carbonwise gardening). • Countrywide regulatory participation processes emphasising mainly one-way citizen consulting may not foster public acceptance or citizen ownership. (e.g., Vanhankaupunginlahti). • There are questions about which actor(s) to disseminate guidance to for a large number of potential NBS users (e.g. Guidelines for carbonwise gardening).

4.5.5 Region

The regional scale in between country and city evoked only a few notes, both on potentials as listed in [Table 31](#).

Table 31. Summary of NBS / NEB innovations with regional scalability potential

NBS / NEB INNOVATIONS WITH REGIONAL SCALABILITY POTENTIAL
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding and connecting NBS as complementary networks can create cumulative impacts and is a potential tool for upscaling (see A frame for understanding to better link nature-based solutions and urban planning). • Decision support tools for different administrators for replicating projects have great potential (e.g., OPTimising FOrEst management decisions).

4.5.6 City

The city scale was the most present in the mapped sources. Several types of NBS were seen as potentially scalable specifically at the city scale. Upscaling by continuity and mainstreaming was the biggest theme for both potentials and restrictions. Some participation challenges were raised.

The potential for NBS upscaling (see [Table 32](#)) was mainly related to water management, urban greening and soil design. Water management solutions such as vertical greenery systems, sponge retrofits, introduction of more-than-human agents in river restoration (beavers’ dams), de-paving and green parking, aimed mainly for water management. Heat island mitigation was found to be conducted by city wide urban tree planting (though as noted above in [Table 26](#), the Miyawaki example must be done with care to be successful).

City-scale upscaling restrictions (see [Table 33](#)) included policy-makers potentially prioritising real estate developers during city development instead of NBS actions and finding strong enough validation to support NBS over real estate development may be difficult.

Table 32. Summary of NBS / NEB innovations with city scalability potential

NBS / NEB INNOVATIONS WITH CITY SCALABILITY POTENTIAL
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vertical NBS are vertical greenery systems for evapotranspiration as stormwater management for densely built areas (Lausen et al. 2022). • Integrating water retention into landscapes include sponge retrofits, de-paving, green parking, expanding green zones (e.g., Spongeworks). • Urban tree planting at the city scale by Paris Plan Arbre included 700km of street sides planted in 2024 and was enhanced with 10 essential commitments to treat the trees better, such as identity cards for trees, medicines, diversity of tree species considering climate change, protection during construction work (see Plan Arbre).

(continued overleaf)

Table 32 continued

- According to the residents of the Berlin Baumscheibenfest event, only the necessary facilitation is needed by municipality officials to keep the NBS activity genuinely bottom up. Bottom-up activity seems to be resilient for the long term due to the history of nearly 30 years of planting in the project (see [Berlin Baumscheibenfest](#)).
- An areal green factor tool helps to assess and enhance green infrastructure within municipality scale (see Kassi et al., 2025; [ARVO](#)).
- Policy briefs were highlighted for supporting policymaking at the city-scale (e.g., [Just trees](#)).
- Local ecosystem service modelling and scenario tools strengthened planning decisions and helped mainstream NBS, such as de-paving and regreening into municipal policies and can also be conducted at city scale (e.g., [ReGreen](#)).
- Accelerating NBS/NEB adaptation by engaging authorities in cross disciplinary, cross city workshops and learning for scaling-up at the city scale (e.g., [Greenstorm](#)).
- Enduring commitment by the municipality and the city housing company helped the Eco City Augustenborg project to sustain longer (see Månsson & Persson 2021; [Eco city Augustenborg](#)).
- Partnerships between key authorities helps scalability and car traffic regulation, storm water management and greening by urban tree planting and opening surfaces (e.g., [Barcelona superblocks](#)).
- Alliances with existing government programs and processes at city scale are good to have (e.g. [CONEXUS](#)).

Table 33. Restrictions and limitations of city scalability of NBS

RESTRICTIONS / LIMITATIONS (WHAT TO LOOK OUT FOR?)

- Non-scalability of face-to-face participation: face-to-face engagement for residents supported by expert knowledge were found effective for gaining acceptance of NBS and developing transformational agency. But these types of events can be difficult to upscale. Bigger participatory events potentially end up being one-way information events (e.g., [Plüschke-Altöf et al. 2025](#)).
- Validating NBS for policy makers: NBS are subsidiary to growth for municipalities that prioritise real estate developers' needs (e.g., [Plüschke-Altöf et al. 2025](#)).
- A limitation of applying NEB values is the lack of institutionalising co-creation; co-creation is conducted only during projects and hasn't become mainstream in municipal processes (e.g., [Clever Cities](#)).
- NBS / NEB development on private land is usually restricted for the authorities, limiting interventions (e.g., [Greenstorm](#)).
- Adaptive, community rooted models can require long-term political and financial support which may be difficult to acquire (e.g., [Prinzezzingärten](#)).
- Difficulty of cooperation across different work cultures, for instance, disciplinary research habits, societal and government problems solving rationalities, different cultural values, different sector's goals (e.g., [CONEXUS](#)).
- Upscaling and long-term resilience of NBS calls for formal adaptation by the governing officials (e.g., [OpSkalAR](#)).
- Green gentrification is a potential unintended consequence. Restricting car traffic in developing green areas may lead to more car traffic in the city's outskirts (e.g., [Barcelona superblocks](#)).

4.5.7 Neighbourhood

Neighbourhood scale potentials highlighted included small scale suitable NBS and grass roots level engagement. Prejudices were presented as an example of a potential barrier for gaining acceptance for NBS at a neighbourhood scale.

Table 34. Summary of NBS / NEB innovations with neighbourhood scalability potential

NBS / NEB INNOVATIONS WITH NEIGHBOURHOOD SCALABILITY POTENTIAL
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote spaces for environmental education (e.g., CONEXUS). • Evapotranspiration based NBS perform well for small to medium rain events and are suitable for small scale interventions that can be part of a larger strategy or a network of NBS (see e.g., Lausen et al. 2022). • Face to face engagement with expert support is effective to raise environmental awareness and gain access for NBS with local citizens and other stakeholders. (see Plüschke-Altöf et al. 2025). • Adaptive, community rooted models such as urban gardening can create strong environmental and social benefits but require long term political and financial support (e.g., Prinzezzingärten).

Table 35. Restrictions and limitations of neighbourhood scalability of NBS

RESTRICTIONS / LIMITATIONS (WHAT TO LOOK OUT FOR?)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prejudice towards NBS when solutions can be seen as “too green”, not tidy enough and even dangerous places with snakes and ticks (see Plüschke-Altöf et al. 2025).

4.5.8 Landscape

Landscapes include the intersection of multiple ecological and associated social systems (e.g. a river valley, forests) which do not fit neatly into administrative boundaries, often including a mix of regional and local governance, and public and private ownership. Approaching NBS through the scale of the landscape allows for strategic interventions that can work together to have a positive impact on wider ecosystems.

At the same time, landscapes have strong cultural associations, which can be mobilised along with NEB values to encourage citizen participation at larger scales. Potentials and limitations of upscaling at the landscape level are summarised in [Table 36](#) and [Table 37](#) respectively.

Table 36. Summary of NBS / NEB innovations with landscape scalability potential

NBS / NEB INNOVATIONS WITH LANDSCAPE SCALABILITY POTENTIAL
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Punctual interventions can work towards common goals such as collective work on a mountain stone wall using traditional techniques on private land to counter soil erosion on a mountain (e.g., TRANSlighthouses). This also has the potential to empower local communities to learn how to relearn traditional knowledge linked to shared natural heritage linked to landscapes (e.g. forest, mountain). • While systemic transformations involving many stakeholders can take a long time to implement, NBS such as creating riparian buffer strips or widening areas to retain water can already be incorporated on private land, allowing for new synergies between landowners and NBS beneficiaries along the river system (e.g., LAND4CLIMATE).

Table 37. Restrictions and limitations of landscape scalability of NBS

RESTRICTIONS / LIMITATIONS (WHAT TO LOOK OUT FOR?)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complex governance with multiple actors and stakeholders operating at different scales can make coordination difficult and cause barriers to implementation. • Landscapes in transformation can sometimes challenge existing cultural attachments. How to incorporate innovation and new landscape forms while preserving historical and traditional associations is a key question. • Long-term planning in relation to ‘place-keeping’ often falls out of the timeframe of projects where funding often has to be spent within a short amount of time, while evaluation of ‘success’ may be best measured much later. There is an opportunity to develop ‘work-arounds’ in budgets to allow for slower timelines which allow communities to get on board (see e.g., Dempsev, N., & Burton, M. 2012.).

4.5.9 All scales

Some findings for the all scales category overlapped with scale specific potentials or restrictions which helped to identify common themes in the mapping. Notable common discussion topics in the workshop considering all scales were that **processes, methods and approaches scale better than the nature-based solutions themselves** due to contextual limitations and that **local citizen engagement is always relevant**. More in [Table 38](#).

Additionally, a commonly acknowledged barrier was that reporting only the **positive outcomes and lessons dominate many reports and make learning harder for follow-up projects**. For more see [Table 39](#).

Table 38. Summary of NBS / NEB innovations with potential for all scales

NBS / NEB INNOVATIONS WITH POTENTIAL TO CONSIDER WITHIN ALL SCALES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small scale community driven NBS should be prioritised and supported because they are long term sustainable and inclusive that are a solid base for scaling up (see The Natura Global Roadmap, Urban Nature-Based Solutions: European report). • Accessible learning of lessons should be built into NBS to be easily replicated (see Frantzeskaki 2018; Resilient Europe). • Different guides and methods for different stakeholders and scales were highlighted as useful; “downscaling the language” and ensuring that different actors understand concepts of NBS (see Plüschke-Altof et al. 2025). • Analysing ownership, partners and governance and applying the learnings is more scalable than context specific NBS (see Dempsev, N., & Burton, M. 2012). • Linking health benefits can improve acceptance and participation (e.g., Naturelab). • Data-driven decision-making tools are relevant in all scales (e.g. Urbreath). • Long-term resilience depends on monitoring, actor commitment, and shared ownership of maintenance/care beyond the build phase (e.g., EcoAdvance). • Innovative approaches for caring about the non-human, e.g. Writing love letters to trees (a general note relevant in all scales). • Using the site as a testbed for on-site testing of the NBS before finalising the solution helps to gain knowledge of the context and enables deeper iteration and participation already during the process (see Allik 2021; Jubileumsparken).

Table 39. Restrictions and limitations of NBS at all scales

RESTRICTIONS / LIMITATIONS (WHAT TO LOOK OUT FOR?)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Private funding is insufficient, NBS is seen as high risk investments and the EU remains as the main funder which may contribute to mainstreaming difficulties (The Natura Global Roadmap, Urban Nature-Based Solutions: European report). • Short-term funding hinders long-term project objectives (a common note). For example the length and inadaptability of processes means that objectives may become less relevant during many years of projects (e.g., Co-Carbon). • In any successful case of NBS, the barrier may be the dissemination of innovations to integrate or commercialise them in a wider scale in everyday life (see Månsson & Persson 2021; Eco city Augustenborg). • Scaling depends on long-term technical maintenance (e.g., Essenburgpark). • Working collectively on private land may be challenging (e.g., Translighthouses). • The solutions are often not very scalable due to contextual limitations, ecological, climatic consideration etc. Holistic understanding is required to scale up sustainably (see Vega et al. 2021; Seeds fall). • Experimental development often takes place in temporary developing settings which can threaten long term sustainability (e.g. De Ceuvel).

5. SOURCES

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Barcelona Superblocks. <https://ajuntament.barcelona.cat/superilles/en> and <https://citylabbcn.org/masterclass/>

Berlin Baumscheibenfest. <https://baumscheibenfest.de/ueber-uns.html>

Carbon Gardening. <https://cocarbon.fi/en/research/home-yard-carbon-gardening/>

City Blues. <https://interreg-baltic.eu/project/city-blues/>

CLEVER Cities. <https://clevercities.eu/>

Clever cities guidance. <https://clevercities.eu/clever-guidance-sub/index/>

CO-CARBON. <https://cocarbon.fi/en/>

Co-Evolvers. <https://co-evolvers.eu/>

CONEXUS. <https://networknature.eu/conexus>

Curieuzeneuzen. <https://curieuzeneuzen.be/home-en/>

CoolGreen. <https://www.aalto.fi/en/landscape-architecture/coolgreen>

DeCeutel. <https://deceutel.nl/en/about/zoop-de-ceutel/>

EcoAdvance. <https://ecoadvance.eu/>

Eläköön kaupunkimaaperä! Kohti maaperälähtöistä suunnittelua.

<https://www.vmparistotiedonfoorumi.fi/elakoon-kaupunkimaapera-kohti-maaperälahtoista-suunnittelua/>

Erillään katoamme -hanke / Mikrometsä. <https://koneensaatio.fi/apurahat-ja-residenssipaiikat/erillaan-katoamme-hanke-mikrometsa/>

Essenburgpark. <https://www.essenburgpark.nl/>

euPOLIS. <https://eupolis-project.eu/>

FairNature. <https://fairnatureproject.com/>

From Grey to Green. <https://www.greytogreen.org.uk>

Gammare collective. <https://www.collectifdesgammare.com/>

Green Climate Screen. <https://stateofgreen.com/en/solutions/green-climate-screen/>

Greenstorm. <https://arceau-idf.fr/en/projects/greenstorm>

Grey to Green Sheffield. <https://www.greytogreen.org.uk/>

Grow Green Modena. <https://networknature.eu/growgreen>

Hiedanranta. <https://hiedanranta.fi/en/>

IN-HABIT. <https://networknature.eu/in-habit>
 Jubileumsparken. <https://www.goteborg.com/en/places/jubileumsparken>
 JustTrees. <https://sites.utu.fi/justtrees/en/>
 Land4Climate. <https://networknature.eu/land4climate>
 Lehmusruuusu. <https://teemulehmusruuusu.com/>
 Les Tartres. <https://plainecommune.fr/projets/grands-projets-urbains/les-tartres/>
 Manor Fields Park and Green Estate. <https://greenestate.org.uk/ugp-manor-fields-park/>
 MUST. <https://must-project.fi/home/>
 Natura Global Roadmap. <https://www.nbsroadmap.org/roadmap>
 Urban Nature-Based Solutions: European report. <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1-HRvPdQnarsHKu6lYlLwGLjXShlMUP0o/view>
 Nature4Cities. <https://www.nature4cities.eu/the-n4c-project>
 Naturelab. <https://naturelab-project.eu/>
 Nature Perspectives. <https://www.natureperspectives.earth/>
 Nekalan paahdeverkosto, Tampere. <https://villivyohyke.fi/nekalan-paahdeverkosto/>
 Network Nature Reservoir. <https://networknature.eu/networknature/projects>
 OpSkaLAR. <https://akb-kbh.dk/nvheder/aabning-opskalar-kunst-klima-faellesskab-moedes-lundtoftegade>
 Plan Arbre. <https://www.paris.fr/pages/l-arbre-a-paris-199#le-plan-arbre>
 Prinzessingärten kollektiv Berlin. <https://prinzessinnengarten-kollektiv.net/>
 REGREEN. <https://networknature.eu/regreen>
 ReWET. www.rewet.info
 Resilient Europe. <https://urbact.eu/networks/resilient-europe>
 Rights of the Mother Earth. <https://www.boell.de/en/2025/01/29/rights-mother-earth-bolivia-progress-and-challenges>
 RISE. <https://www.rise-program.org/>
 RISE-INN. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101214441>
 Sheffield Street Tree Partnership. <https://sheffieldstreettreepartnership.org/>
 Sleeping Beauty. <https://www.sleepingbeauty-project.eu/>
 Spongeworks. <https://www.spongeworks.eu/>
 TERRRA. <https://terra.org/>
 The Natura Global Roadmap. <https://www.nbsroadmap.org/roadmap>
 Trans4num. <https://trans4num.eu/en/>
 TRANS-lighthouses. <https://trans-lighthouses.eu/>
 TreesAI. <https://treesainfrastructure.com/>
 Urban Nature Atlas. <https://una.city/>
 Urban nature-based solutions: European report. <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1-HRvPdQnarsHKu6lYlLwGLjXShlMUP0o/view>
 URBREATH. <https://networknature.eu/urbreath>
 URBREATH project. <https://urbreath.eu/>
 Vantaa Tree Policy. <https://www.vantaa.fi/fi/asuminen-ja-rakentaminen/kadut-ja-puistot/vantaan-katupuuliniaus/hinnasto-katupuiden-vaurioiden-korvaamisesta>
 Vanhankaupunginlahti.
https://oppla.eu/sites/default/files/old_files/uploads/17helsinkiupload.pdf
 VERDIR. <https://www.slideshare.net/slideshow/etat-des-lieux-du-projet-verdir-lige/98573077>
 Water Framework Directive.
https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/water/water-framework-directive_en

6. APPENDIX

6.1 Resource database list

Below is the full resource database list of the 100 mapped sources that were part of feeding into the key lessons learned in this document. This list is also available as an Open Access Database [here](#), which includes short summary reflections that were the starting point of the mapping exercise undertaken by partners across all five European countries, as described in Section 3: [Data collection and analyses methods](#).

	Resource Link	Short description
1	https://cocarbon.fi/tutkimus/kotipihan-hiilikortisto/	Guidelines for Carbon-wise Gardening
2	https://www.ymparistotiedonfoorumi.fi/elakoon-kaupunkimaapera-kohti-maaperalahtoista-suunnittelua/	Finnish state of the art in relation to living soil approach
3	Erillään katoamme -hanke / Mikrometsä - Koneen Säätö	One of the projects of a Finnish collective of researchers and artists, to make soil alive again
4	https://www.aalto.fi/en/landscape-architecture/just-trees	JustTrees (project)
5	https://www.aalto.fi/en/landscape-architecture/coolgreen	CoolGreen (project)
6	https://figbc.fi/media/rakennetun-ympariston-luontotyypit-luonnos_2025_arvo-hanke.pdf	ARVO (project)
7	https://cocarbon.fi/en/research/urbantreemanifesto/	CO-CARBON's urban tree manifesto and tree canopy cover atlas
8	https://must-project.fi/home/	MUST (project)
9	https://www.biwe.fi/en/home/	BIWE (project)
10	www.cocarbon.fi	Co-Carbon (project)
11	Several cases under one link: https://www.mdpi.com/2073-445X/14/8/1649	Augmented Urbans - Courtyard meadows (Unpacking Tensions in Sustainable City Development in Northern Europe)
12		Augmented Urbans - street axis (Unpacking Tensions in Sustainable City Development in Northern Europe)
13		Augmented Urbans - Bee Corridor (Findings from the article Unpacking Tensions in Sustainable City Development in Northern Europe)
14		Augmented Urbans - Main Street (Findings from the article Unpacking Tensions in Sustainable City Development in Northern Europe)
15		Augmented Urbans - Riverfront (Findings from the article Unpacking Tensions in Sustainable City Development in Northern Europe)
16		GoGreenRoutes - Active Mobility (Findings from the article Unpacking Tensions in Sustainable City Development in Northern Europe)
17		GoGreenRoutes - Nearby greenery (Findings from the article Unpacking Tensions in Sustainable City Development in Northern Europe)

18	https://oppla.eu/sites/default/files/old_files/uploads/17helsinkiupload.pdf	Vanhankaupunginlahti, Old Town Bay - Finland
19	https://www.mareldarkitektur.se/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/Project-Process-Park_Book_small.pdf	Jubileumsparken, Göteborg Sweden
20	https://deceuveel.nl/en/about/general-information/	De Ceuveel, Amsterdam, Netherlands
21	https://www.ravon.nl/Portals/2/Bestanden/Publicaties/Rapporten/2020.039.pdf	Vistrap Wolvenvallei
22	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1462901118310888	The Resilient Europe project funded by URBACT 2015-2018 /11 cities experiment NBS as alternative for infrastructure re-development & NBS as alternative to grey infrastructure. Article: Frantzeskaki, N. (2019). Seven lessons for planning nature-based solutions in cities. Environmental science & policy, 93, 101-111
23	https://www.essenburgpark.nl	Essenburgpark
24	https://prinzessinnengarten-kollektiv.net	Prinzezzingärten, Berlin
25	https://clevercities.eu/ + https://clevercities.eu/clever-guidance-sub/index/	Clever Cities green corridors, gardens and other solutions in three cities, Hamburg, London, Milan.
26	https://plainecommune.fr/projets/grands-projets-urbains/les-tartres/	Les Tartes, area of three municipalities in Seine-Saint-Denis.
27	https://interreg-baltic.eu/project/city-blues/	City Blues Interreg project 2023-2026 in Tampere, Tartu, Malmö, Aarhus & Stavanger.
28	https://arceau-idf.fr/en/projects/greenstorm	Greenstorm: Design and Deployment of Stormwater Nature-Based Solutions for Resilient and Liveable Cities.
29	https://nph.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/ppp3.10191	Where Seeds Fall: Citizen science project from Zürich
30	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1462901123001247	A frame for understanding to better link nature-based solutions and urban planning
31	https://www.greytogreen.org.uk	From Grey to Green in Sheffield (ICE Manual of Blue-Green Infrastructure, 2023, Case studies of blue-green infrastructure in spatial planning, doi: 10.1680/ icembi.65420.287)
32	https://openresearch.amsterdam/en/page/74758/biodivercity_a-matter-of-vital-soil	BiodiverCITY_A Matter of Vital Soil!
33	https://baumscheibenfest.de	Berlin Baumscheibenfest yearly event for local trees and their surroundings. Tips for dwellers to take care of the trees in the city.
34	https://fairnatureproject.com	Fair Nature (project, biodiversa) - most updated resource: https://pureportal.inbo.be/en/publications/fairnature-stakeholder-engagement-strategy/
35	https://connectingnature.eu/	Connecting Nature (project)
36	https://growgreenproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/D3.3-Nature-based-Solutions-Strategies.pdf	Grow Green (project)
37	D1.4-Intervention-conclusions-Manchester.pdf	Grow Green Manchester demo: The park that drinks water
38	https://growgreenproject.eu/city-actions/valencia/	Grow Green Valencia demo: NBS' in the Benicalap neighborhood
39	https://growgreenproject.eu/city-actions/wroclaw/	Grow Green Wroclaw demo

INNATURE

40	https://growgreenproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/Growgreen_Brest.pdf	Grow Green Brest
41	https://growgreenproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/GrowGreen_Modena.pdf	Grow Green Modena
42	https://growgreenproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/GrowGreen_Zadar.pdf	Grow Green Zadar
43	https://naturvation.eu/about.html	NATURVATION (project)
44	https://una.city/nbs/liege/vegetable-and-plant-production-industrial-wastelands	VERDRIR
45	https://northsearegion.eu/media/23780/immerse-wp47-final-version-may-2023.pdf	Gårda pilot rain garden
46	http://hdl.handle.net/10138/304845 (https://www.helsinki.fi/en/researchgroups/nature-based-solutions/projects/kota)	KOTA-project 2017-2018 (funded by Helsinki Metropolitan Region Urban Research Program)
47	https://una.city/nbs/munster/green-roof-research-university-munster	ReWam
48	https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/7a34e1dd-9db6-11f0-97c8-01aa75ed71a1/language-en	Network Nature publication
49	https://unalab.eu/en/our-cities	Urban Nature Labs (UNALAB)
50	https://co-evolvers.eu/	Coevolvers (EU-project)
51	https://www.nbsroadmap.org/roadmap	The Natura Global Roadmap on Urban Nature-Based Solutions: European report
52	https://networknature.eu/urbreath	URBREATH (EU-project)
53	https://trans-lighthouses.eu/en	TRANSlighthouses
54	https://networknature.eu/resonate	RESONATE
55	https://networknature.eu/regreenation	ReGreenaration
56	https://networknature.eu/regreen	REGREEN
57	https://www.naturescapes-project.com/	NatureScapes (project) - most updated resources: https://www.naturescapes-project.com/resources
58	https://naturelab-project.eu/	NATURELAB
59	https://www.nature4cities.eu/	Nature4Cities
60	https://nature-demo.eu/	Nature-Demo
61	https://multisource.eu/	MULTISOURCE
62	https://www.greenincities.eu/	GreeninCities - most updated resources: https://www.greenincities.eu/s/D17_Values-and-Ethics-Handbook_GreenInCities.pdf and https://www.greenincities.eu/tools
63	https://networknature.eu/in-habit	IN-HABIT
64	https://networknature.eu/land4climate	LANDFORCLIMATE
65	https://eupolis-project.eu/	euPOLIS

66	https://www.cardimed-project.eu/	CARDIMED
67	https://networknature.eu/conexus	CONEXUS
68	https://ecoadvance.eu/	EcoAdvance
69	https://trans4num.eu/en/	trans4num
70	https://www.spongeworks.eu/	SpongeWorks
71	https://www.desirmed.eu/	DesirMED
72	https://ajuntament.barcelona.cat/superilles/en	Barcelona Superblocks
73	https://www.paris.fr/pages/l-arbre-a-paris-199#le-plan-arbre	Paris Plan Arbre
74	https://www.vantaa.fi/fi/asuminen-ja-rakentaminen/kadut-ja-puistot/vantaan-katupuulinjaus/hinnasto-katupuiden-vaurioiden-korvaamisesta	Urban Tree Policy of Vantaa
75	https://greenestate.org.uk/ugp-manor-fields-park/	Manor Fields Park - a case study discussed in Dempsey, N. and Slothower, P. (2025) Sustaining the sense of place: challenges in long-term management, Chapter 15, in J. Woudstra and X. Ren (eds.) Case studies in architecture and landscape: expanding the legacy of Peter Blundell Jones. Edited by. London: Routledge, pp. 186-196.
76	http://rewildmystreet.org/letsgetrewild	London Let's Get Rewild
77	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2011.09.005	Dempsey, N. and Burton, M. (2012) Defining place-keeping: the long-term management of public spaces, Urban Forestry and Urban Greening, 11(1): 11-21.
78	https://sheffieldstreettreepartnership.org/	Sheffield Street Tree Partnership
79	www.rewet.info	ReWET (Climate-impacted Dweller-led Agroecological Stewardship for Restoring Wetlands)
80	https://www.natureperspectives.earth/	Nature Perspectives, Cambridge University
81	https://www.rise-program.org/	RISE (Revitalising Informal Settlements and their Environments), Monash University
82	https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/entities/publication/ed023e93-3872-474c-b67b-4a19f6f857e8	Growing Resilience: Unlocking the Potential of Nature-based Solutions for Climate Resilience in Sub-Saharan Africa
83	https://data.jncc.gov.uk/data/376d989f-0563-4e7f-b034-c79108f63758/nbs-triple-win-toolkit.pdf	Nature-based Solutions Triple Win Toolkit
84	Own project	OpSkaLAR - Scaling up of NBSsw from niche level to main system in Copenhagen
85	https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1571679/FULLTEXT01.pdf	The Eco-city Augustenborg - experiences and lessons learned Editors: Monika Månsson and Bengt Persson
86	https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/1573062X.2012.668913	Fratini, C. F., Geldof, G. D., Kluck, J., & Mikkelsen, P. S. (2012). Three Points Approach (3PA) for urban flood risk management: A tool to support climate change adaptation through transdisciplinarity and

		multifunctionality. <i>Urban Water Journal</i> , 9(5), 317-331. https://doi.org/10.1080/1573062X.2012.668913
87	https://iwaponline.com/bgs/article/4/2/326/92469/Into-the-air-a-freestanding-vertical-greenery	Lausen E.D, Jensen M.B, Randall M.T.; Into the air: a freestanding vertical greenery system (VGS) for evapotranspiration (ET) of roof runoff. <i>Blue-Green Systems</i> 1 December 2022; 4 (2): 326-339. doi: https://doi.org/10.2166/bgs.2022.029
88	https://sheffieldstreettreepartnership.org/	Sheffield Street Tree Partnership
89	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2590332220304814	Tony H.F. Wong, Briony C. Rogers, Rebekah R. Brown (2020). "Transforming Cities through Water-Sensitive Principles and Practices" <i>One Earth</i> , Volume 3, Issue 4, Pages 436-447, ISSN 2590-3322, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2020.09.012 .
90	https://www.mdpi.com/2073-445X/14/8/1649	Plüschke-Altof, B., Loewen, B., Calderon, C., Chebotareva, M., Tuula-Fjodorov, R., & Gäckle, J. (2025). Nature-Based Solutions and Public Participation: Unpacking Tensions in Sustainable City Development in Northern Europe. <i>Land</i> , 14(8), 1649. https://doi.org/10.3390/land14081649
91	https://ign.ku.dk/english/paws/?utm_source=chatgpt.com	PaWS - pathways to water resilient South African Cities
92	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101060554/reporting	OPTimising FORest management decisions for a low-carbon, climate resilient future in Europe
93	https://www.naturescapes-project.com/	NATURESCAPES
94	https://una.city/nbs/timisoara/ecological-reconstruction-lamaita-pond	Ecological reconstruction of the Lămăița pond
95	https://prizes.new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/application/faget-forest-park-cluj-green-lung; doi: 10.3389/fenvs.2021.618217	Făget Forest Park; Cluj's Green Lung (URBforDAN project)
96	PDF	Les techniques de restauration Low-Tech et basées sur la régénération des processus, quelle application sur les cours d'eau du Bassin Rhône - Méditerranée et Corse ?
97	https://treesinfrastructure.com/	TreesAI
98	https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S037811272200336X	Forest restoration and hydrology
99	https://journals.openedition.org/dynenviron/8606	Hydrologie Régénérative : Méthodologie de quantification des impacts pour les sites pilotes / Regenerative Hydrology: Methodology for Quantifying Impacts on Pilot Sites
100	https://www.soilcarenetwork.com/soiltalks-5	SoilTalk 5 "Nature based solutions: soil-water connections for sustainable landscapes

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